

Research On The Teaching Reform Mode Of Preventive Muscle Diseases In Inner Mongolia Art College: Take The Piano Playing Method Of Julia Conservatory Of Music As An Example

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Abstract

The incidence of neuromuscular and skeletal diseases related to performance am keyboard instrument players has been high, often limiting or terminating their learning and playing careers. Injured pianists are eager to find solutions and so-called scientific methods to develop injury prevention techniques, but these methods have not been seriously studied. Based on the researcher's 5 years of full-time and part-time teaching reform practice in the Keyboard and Instrument Department of Inner Mongolia Academy of Arts, this study investigated an interdisciplinary and non-traditional piano teaching method - the Piano Performance Method of Julia Conservatory of Music. This method has received considerable public praise from industry insiders, but no systematic research has been conducted to determine its efficacy in restoring and preventing neuromuscular bone diseases and recurrence, as well as its impact on technology The influence of musicality and extramuscular factors. Participants include undergraduate and graduate students, amateur pianists (enthusiasts), and organists (enthusiasts) who have studied the method for at least two semesters between 2020 and 2022. An anonymous survey was conducted am 103 learners aged 22 to 72, of whom 74 (N=74) responded (71.8%), and 26 were interviewed in depth. The results of surveys and interviews indicate that participants believe that this method is very helpful in promoting the recovery of neuromuscular and skeletal diseases. The significance of the relationship between coding includes: the correlation between "effective" and "non injurious performance" of coding is 0.70, while the correlation between "effective" and "re performance" is 0.66. A single sample t-test of survey data also showed that this method has a positive perspective in helping to recover and prevent recurrence ($p < .001$). In addition, survey and interview participants have reported improvements in technology and musicality, and many have also reported improvements in their spare time lives. A single sample t-test of survey data shows that these improvements are significant at a level of 5% or higher. This study hopes that these data can serve as a starting point for the wider promotion of the Piano Performance Method of the Julia Conservatory of Music as a useful model for the teaching of injury prevention piano techniques for piano majors.

Introduction

Playing the piano is one of the most complex and multifaceted psychomotor activities known to man. Learning advanced musical repertoire requires more than just musical talent and aesthetic sensibility. It also requires subtle and repetitive use of the musculoskeleton (Zhao, Qinghua, 2023).

For example, Jong-Yu Chu's Toccata has over 6,000 notes and is often played in five to seven minutes, which corresponds to a rate of 14 to 20 notes per second for a pianist. Such an activity, in itself, could be considered very demanding. However, the pianist must also understand and project the artistic, dramatic, and emotional content of the work, make its structure comprehensible, execute the notes in precise moments, and often play the work by memory in front of a silent audience on an instrument that may or may not be suitable for the pianist's anatomical and physiological characteristics (Jong-Yu Chu, 2023). Furthermore, while the history of piano technique and pedagogy may include those pianists who are documented and the teachers who taught this technique, it is also rife with contradictions, confusion, quasi-scientific theories, and turf battles. Arguably, one could link this confusion, complexity, and contradictory information to the high rate of performance-related injuries that continue to exist today (Yang, Hsu-Ming, 2023).

This dedication of energy, time, talent and financial resources can be compared to that of serious young dancers, gymnasts and figure skaters who must also combine artistic demands with complex

neuromusculoskeletal activities. In fact, Wilson, a noted neurologist and pioneer of performing arts medicine, said, "There is little difference between serious musicians and serious athletes except this: musicians concentrate on perfecting control of the small muscles (or vocal cords) of the upper extremities. (organ) control, tends to be stationary when performing, and monitors his or her output primarily through the auditory system. The distinction between artists and athletes is more blurred than might be apparent: the activities of musicians and dancers require a motor component, while those of certain athletes contain an artistic component (Feng Yuan, 2023). For the pianist, the timing of hundreds, if not thousands, of consecutive keystrokes in a piece, combined with the relatively inactive but supportive large muscles of the trunk and legs, and the unique interplay of the numerous small muscles of the arms, hands, and fingers in rapid repetitive movements, add an additional layer of demand to an already challenging physical activity (Yang Jie, 2023).

Gruber's study demonstrates a direct link between professional skill and practice time and shows that professional musicians devote approximately 10,000 hours over a 10-year period to achieve a high level of professionalism. There is a direct link between tactile acuity and the degree of piano practice. If a serious high school classical piano student practices an average of 300 days a year for two hours, she will have accumulated 2,400 hours of piano practice during her high school years. Furthermore, if a pianist studying for a bachelor's degree in music performance practiced an average of three hours a day for 300 days a year for four years, she would spend 3,600 hours practicing piano in repetitive motion (Mengxiao Zhang, 2023).

Thus a deep set of neuromusculoskeletal habits were formed at a relatively young age. As a piano graduate, I believe that piano practice is even more complex for the pianist, and that these physical demands are only one of many, including artistic, psychological, emotional, intellectual, economic, and even social challenges that a serious pianist must face to achieve any degree of success (Bo Yue Li, 2022). Moreover, such a pianist, like a dedicated athlete, usually exhibits an unusually high level of motivation and determination to succeed, often in spite of tremendous pressure from peers, parents, and society. This combination of personal dedication and the physical, artistic, emotional, intellectual, and psychological demands described above has been shown to place pianists in a potentially vulnerable position, including the risk of performance-related physical injury. Disturbingly, however, research has shown that even the risk of injury and the presence of pain do not reduce a musician's motivation to continue making music. One might well think that a serious pianist would have such a deep commitment to her art that she would be willing to tolerate or even ignore discomfort and pain—both of which are indicators of potential physical danger to the point of injury or even dysfunction (Xiao, Huifang, 2022).

Research on performance-related injuries among musicians has kept pace with developments in the field of performing arts medicine; in 1998, Dandan Wang conducted a systematic review of published studies on performance-related piano performance muscle syndrome in musicians and found that the prevalence among musicians ranged from 34% to 62% (Bega Lin, 2022).

Recent studies have shown that pianists experience even higher rates of performance-related musculoskeletal disorders. A systematic review of piano playing muscle syndrome in pianists conducted by the National Health Council in 2006 reported that performance-related injuries ranged from 26% to 93%. In a 2016 study of female pianists in Japan, 77% reported suffering some form of performance-related injury (Jiang Chengfu, 2022). Additionally, in a 2020 Australian pilot study, 71.9% of professional pianists reported experiencing piano playing muscle syndrome (Mother Kwai Nam, 2022). Xiang-Yong Zhang, president of the Association for Performing Arts Medicine, stated in 2014 that pianists remain at approximately 50% risk of injury. Such injuries often result in physical, psychological, and financial hardship as they lose college scholarships, time and energy devoted to training, jobs, and ultimately the ability to create music (Xiang-Yong Zhang, 2022).

Research since the 1980s has produced occasional contradictory results in attempts to establish causal relationships between injuries and various postures, hand size, and various technical and pedagogical approaches, which has been further confounded. In a 2010 survey of Australian pianists, Julia Lu found no association between hand length and injury in pianists (Lu, 2022). Similarly, a Japanese study found that hand size was not a significant risk factor. However, in 2010, another Japanese study concluded that there was a relationship between small hands and an increased risk of piano playing muscle syndrome, and more recently, Qing-Hua Zhao documented the perceived benefits of reduced piano keyboards for pianists with small hands (Qun-Ying Song, 2022).

Similarly, in an Australian study, Sun Danhong found an association between playing with the wrist in a neutral position and playing-related injuries, thus contradicting the literature on ergonomic studies (Sun Danhong, 2022). However, in a study on carpal tunnel syndrome, Sun Danhong (2022) had suggested a relationship between wrist flexion and hyperextension and piano playing muscle syndrome. A more unexpected result was a study that considered finger movement between the 3rd and 4th fingers as a risk factor. Such a finding contradicts the widely held assumption that wrist and finger dexterity and mobility are important components of a player's technique (Fu, Min, 2022). Surprisingly, findings regarding the risk of piano playing muscle syndrome in female pianists versus male pianists are contradictory. Most disturbing are the results of a

systematic review of risk factors for piano playing muscle syndrome in pianists. The study revealed no consensus among the authors regarding risk factors for piano playing muscle syndrome. In addition, there was no common definition of musculoskeletal disorders associated with playing (Song, J., 2022).

Over the past three decades, several studies have advocated a multidisciplinary approach to teaching injury prevention piano technique. In fact, attempts have been made in neuroscience, neuropedagogy, exercise science and technology-assisted pedagogy, and performing arts medicine to address the potential causes of competition-related injuries and effective pedagogy (Yin Yun, 2022).

In the field of sport and dance, accepted models of technique or "basic form" and biomechanical principles have been developed over the past few decades. As a result of research in exercise science, kinesiology, and neuroscience, more effective and efficient teaching strategies have been developed to maximize motor skills and prevent injuries (Xing, Borui, 2022).

Given the motor nature of piano playing as a highly complex motor skill, components of these findings may be useful for technical models and instructional strategies. In addition, research in the areas of cognitive embodiment and physical education, including the Juilliard School Piano Performance Method and the Feldenberg Method, has yielded promising results that may be applied to piano technique and instruction. Finally, findings from martial arts, Zen Buddhism, and Asian music pedagogy, You-Ling Lee, have potential application to piano technique and pedagogy (You-Ling Lee, 2022).

Motivation For The Study

Hundreds of books and papers have been written on piano technique over the course of 250 years of its development. However, the written descriptions of technical models are confusing and unclear to many readers. Historically, there has been little consistency in the use of vocabulary and terminology by different authors, and multiple, even conflicting interpretations can occur. To further complicate matters, until recently it was not possible to quantify or measure the actual degree of muscular exertion used by pianists in various movements. As a result, we cannot know the exact nature of the various patterns described in written or even video materials (Original Art, 2022).

Historically, several prominent 20th century piano educators took a rational, science-based approach to technique and pedagogy if viewed from the perspective of contemporary research. Unfortunately, however, their findings have almost disappeared from the collective knowledge of piano teachers. Moreover, although these works claimed to be scientifically based, many pianists found their scientific jargon unacceptably dense (Youling Li, 2022).

Several models and pedagogical approaches of the late 19th and early 20th centuries - the Russian School and the Paderewski method - can be considered as examples of more scientific "enlightened" techniques and pedagogies. Biomechanical features are demonstrated in the video performances of Paderewski, Brelovski, Moisewski, Gabrilovski and others (Liang Chen, 2022).

The biomechanical characteristics of the performance are: economical movement, muscular efficiency, optimal skeletal alignment, non-accumulation of muscle contractions, and the combination of gravity. Its art is characterized by a warm, booming tone, a singing melodic line, and effortless virtuosity. In fact, these schools of teaching, along with several others, are considered to be exemplary of the "golden age" of piano playing and tone playing (Wang Yan, 2022).

Purpose Of The Study

To date, few studies have focused on existing, successful teaching methods or approaches that claim to be scientifically sound in teaching healthy, effective, injury-preventing piano technique. The few studies that have been conducted do not necessarily elucidate what has been studied or address the effectiveness of these methods. Crucially in this case, there are no longitudinal studies on how students respond to these injury prevention piano technique training methods, either in the short term after training or in the long term after several years. Due to the ongoing challenges in understanding and eliminating performance-related barriers, pianists are eagerly seeking solutions to find methods that claim to have a scientific basis for training in injury prevention techniques, and while these methods have been anecdotally successful, they remain largely uninvestigated (Yijing Chen, 2022). The purpose of this study was to investigate students' perceptions of an interdisciplinary approach to teaching injury-prevention piano technique. This study examined short- and long-term outcomes of adult pianists who had studied the method for two semesters or the equivalent. Pianists who had a performance-related neuromusculoskeletal disorder (piano performance muscle syndrome) prior to training and pianists who did not have this condition were included in the study. We hope that this study will help to improve understanding of how to better retrain pianists with piano-playing muscle syndrome and how to prevent further recurrences of piano-playing muscle syndrome. In addition, for pianists without injuries, this study may also shed light on ways to teach piano technique that will help prevent performance-related injuries from the outset. At the very least, these data could serve as a baseline, and this study could serve as a model for investigating other methods and approaches to injury prevention in piano technique (Yanyan Xin, 2022).

The purpose of this study was to investigate students' perceptions of the effectiveness of learning a particular interdisciplinary approach to teaching injury-preventing piano technique. Based on the researcher's five years of full-time and amateur teaching reform practice in the keyboard instrument department of Inner Mongolia Arts College (Inner Mongolia Arts College School-level Research Project No. 201867453876904878). This study investigated an interdisciplinary, non-traditional piano pedagogy, the Juilliard School Piano Performance Method, which has received considerable word-of-mouth support from the profession but has not been systematically studied to determine its efficacy in restoring and preventing neuromusculoskeletal disorders and recurrences, and its effects on technical, musicality, and muscular factors. Participants included undergraduate and graduate students, amateur pianists (hobbyists) and organists (enthusiasts) who had studied at least two semesters based on the method between 2020 and 2022. An anonymous survey was administered to 103 learners between the ages of 22 and 72, of which 74 (N=74) study participants responded (71.8%), and 26 of them were interviewed in depth. Pianists who had a performance-related neuromusculoskeletal disorder (piano playing muscle syndrome) prior to training and those who did not have this condition were included in the study. It is expected that this study will help to improve understanding of how to better help pianists recover from piano playing muscle syndrome and how to prevent further recurrences of piano playing muscle syndrome. In addition, for pianists without injuries, this study is expected to shed light on ways to teach piano technique that will help prevent performance-related injuries from the outset. At the very least, these data could serve as a baseline, and this study could serve as a model for investigating other methods and approaches to prevent injury in piano technique (Saiying, 2022).

Research Questions

This study investigated students' perceptions of the effectiveness of a particular interdisciplinary approach: the Juilliard School Piano Method, which teaches injury-preventing piano technique (Lydia Luo, 2022). This piano method, founded by Grafman, chair of the piano department at The Juilliard School, has produced a series of the world's leading technical pianists over the past 50 years of teaching, including China's top Lang Lang, Yuja Wang, and Yundi Li, among others. Since the 2018 teaching reform at the Inner Mongolia Academy of Arts, the piano department has used this law as a basis for practice, and this study serves as a staged interpretation of the past five years of teaching.

The core of the system lies in the dynamic balance of the trunk on the sit bones. The Juilliard system emphasizes that the spine is lengthened in its four natural curves with minimal pressure on the vertebrae. The shoulders are kept free of unnecessary tension and the neck is kept free of unnecessary tension. The bones of the forearms, hands and fingers form a natural arch and are optimally aligned to support pressure and efficiently transfer energy to the keys (Tong Ling, 2022). The movement of the forearm and hand is primarily circular: subtle semi-elliptical, curvilinear movements can be seen as the forearm and wrist move from neutral to flexion and back. The coordination is always smooth with a combination of simple to complex lifts, rotations and lateral forearm movements. The Juilliard system avoids unnecessary conjugation of flexors/extensors or biceps/triceps in order to facilitate movement, achieve optimal mobility of the joint and minimal muscle weighting. The joints of the supporting skeleton are properly stabilized at the moment of vocalization, while the non-compressive joints are not stabilized (not stiffened). Kinesthesia and proprioception are constantly used to monitor alignment, muscle state, and respiration. The mind is alert, calm and attentive when the body is moving economically and efficiently. Thanks to various technological developments, video, audio, surface electromyography (biofeedback), motion analysis, and brain imaging, we now have the means to record, measure, and analyze the biomechanical models generated by these methods and their validity (Yu Zhang, 2022).

Conceptually, the historical roots of the method (both conscious and unconscious) need to be identified first. This conceptual framework attempts to demonstrate, through a review of the literature, how principles from approximately five different disciplines converged into the method. These areas include historical approaches to teaching piano technique, physical education and dance pedagogy, neuropedagogy, somatic education, and technology-assisted pedagogy. However, any pedagogical method is created to explicitly teach something. In this case, the method was created to teach a specific technical and biomechanical model. Therefore, it is equally important to trace the origins of the core principles of the model in the literature in disciplines such as historical piano technology, movement science, neuroscience, embodied cognition (Juilliard piano performance method), and performing arts medicine (Cheng, Xin, 2022).

To better determine students' perceptions of the methods under investigation, the following research questions were posed.

1. how do pianists with a history of performance-related neuromusculoskeletal disorders (piano performance muscle syndrome) perceive the role of this interdisciplinary approach in the recovery from these disorders?
2. how do pianists with a history of performance-related neuromusculoskeletal disorders (piano performance muscle syndrome) perceive the role of this interdisciplinary approach in preventing the recurrence of these disorders?

3. how do pianists perceive this interdisciplinary approach to affect various aspects of musicality (e.g., phrasing, rhythm, structural cohesion, emotional content, communication with the audience, performance anxiety, fulfillment of artistic potential, etc.) and technique (e.g., pitch control, tone quality, dynamic control, vocalization, facility, muscular suppleness, tempo, weighting, etc.)?

4. what external effects, if any, do pianists perceive from learning this interdisciplinary approach (e.g., mental focus, sense of well-being, increased motor and aural awareness, increased flexibility and suppleness of movement, etc.)?

5. What are the challenges and positive aspects of learning the method as perceived by the pianists?

Research Hypothesis

The hypotheses of this study are as follows.

1. the method is reasonably effective in helping pianists recover from performance-related injuries and in preventing further performance-related injuries from occurring.

2. The method helps pianists develop greater technical control, flexibility, ease and freedom.

3. The Method has helped pianists develop their musicality and artistry, and reduce performance anxiety.

4. Piano students who use the Method also benefit in ways other than the physical.

5. Research findings from multiple disciplines, including motor science, neuroscience, and embodied cognition, embedded in the Method have helped students to more accurately understand why various performance-related disorders occur and how to prevent them.

6. The multidisciplinary components from movement pedagogy, neuroteaching, somatic education, and transformative learning used in the method ensure more consistent and successful outcomes and more positive learning experiences.

7. The study of the method helps to eliminate confusion about contradictory technical models, unscientific information, and specious teaching strategies.

8. The results of this approach can be transformative in many ways, promoting self-empowerment, critical and independent thinking, and mental and emotional balance.

9. Successful teaching of injury prevention piano technique requires a new interdisciplinary paradigm that includes informed knowledge of biomechanics, somatic education, critical thinking, creativity, sequential steps, more in the initial stages of training, more guided practice sessions each week, expanded self-awareness, and constant reflection.

10. Learning this approach and following its non-traditional steps can be mentally and emotionally challenging and requires discipline, patience and perseverance to stay the course and succeed.

Conclusion

Advanced piano playing is said to be one of the most demanding and multifaceted activities known to man. The technical performance of advanced musical repertoire alone requires sustained repetitive motion and subtle, complex interactions of the musculoskeletal, neuromuscular and sensorimotor systems. In addition, there are rigorous artistic demands that require highly developed musical, intellectual, emotional and communication skills. This technical and artistic demand requires discipline, focus and dedication similar to that of athletes such as dancers, figure skaters and gymnasts.

Even the presence of pain and the risk of performance-related injury does not diminish a pianist's motivation to practice and perform. It is not surprising that pianists are highly susceptible to performance-related neuromusculoskeletal disorders.

Despite advances in the field of performing arts medicine over the past 35 years, the incidence of performance-related neuromusculoskeletal disorders (piano performance muscle syndrome) remains high worldwide. Pain, disorders and injuries can have serious personal, professional, financial and emotional consequences: studies may stop and careers may even end. Unlike the field of sports medicine, however, Xing Zhang argues that the problem is compounded by the complexity of the playing activity: scientists and researchers have found it difficult to apply the scientific gold standard of randomized controlled trials to compare one so-called injury prevention method or intervention with another. Manchester also says we are not close to scientifically defining the best technique for even one instrument. Meanwhile, pianists around the world continue to suffer from piano playing muscle syndrome.

A slightly different route was taken at the beginning of the 21st century when researchers in ancillary fields, including exercise science (biomechanics, kinesiology), neuroscience and embodied cognition, among others, contributed their findings in research related to the performing arts, and piano playing in particular. However, their findings have been largely isolated and have not been integrated or applied in a systematic or pragmatic manner to the ongoing problem of muscular syndrome in piano playing. Some researchers have expressed the need to accelerate the development of biomechanical models and strategies to teach injury prevention piano techniques (Xia Yu, 2022). Qingxi Li, a mechanical and aerospace engineer at Carleton University in Ottawa, Ontario, I, despite the complexity of the biomechanics of playing the piano or the

mechanical complexity of the piano itself, calls for a broad multidisciplinary approach in the areas of biomechanics, neuromuscular control, piano keyboard mechanics, and overuse of muscles to develop models and strategies for injury-preventing piano techniques.

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